

THE INVESTIGATION ON IMPACT PROPERTIES
OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work an investigation on the variation of impact strength and ductility index of hybrid composites with hybrid ratio and interface number as well as impact hybrid effect is conducted. A model for estimating impact strength is established.

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid composites (abbreviated as HFRP) is one of the advancing tendencies of composite materials. One of the main purposes of hybridization is to improve the impact ductility of composites.

In our experiments, we hybridize glass (GF) and Kevlar (KF) fibres with carbon fibres (CF) to reinforce LER matrix (its failure elongation is 0.78%) and HER matrix (its failure elongation is 1.23%) to fabricate uni-directional laminates (sample parameters are listed in Table 1). They are tested by using instrumental Charpy impact instrument. The load-deformation curve, impact ductility index, impact strength and hybrid effect are obtained.

Table 1 The parameters of hybrid laminates*

LER-C/G or C/K			HER-C/K			
No. of laminates	Form of lay-up	V _{cf} %	No. of laminates	Form of lay-up	V _{cf} %	interface number
GFRP	(G ₁₆) _S	0	KFRP	(K ₁₆) _S	0	0
C-1	(CG ₁₅) _S	3.4	C-1	(CK ₁₅) _S	3.8	2
C-2	(C ₃ G ₁₃) _S	10.9	C-2	(C ₃ K ₁₃) _S	11.9	2
C-3	(C ₅ G ₁₁) _S	19.4	C-3	(C ₅ K ₁₁) _S	21.0	2
C-4	(C ₇ G ₉) _S	29.2	C-4	(C ₇ K ₉) _S	31.0	2
C-5	(C ₉ G ₇) _S	40.5	C-5	(C ₉ K ₇) _S	43.0	2
C-7	(C ₁₃ G ₃) _S	69.6	C-7	(C ₁₃ K ₃) _S	72.0	2
CFRP	(C ₁₆) _S	100	CFRP	(C ₁₆) _S	100	2
C-7	(C ₁₃ K ₃) _S	72.0	B-1	(C ₃ K ₆ C ₄ K ₃) _S	31.0	6
C-5	(C ₉ K ₇) _S	43.0	B-2	(C ₃ K ₃ C ₂ K ₃ C ₂ K ₃) _S	31.0	10
C-4	(C ₇ K ₉) _S	31.0	B-3	(C ₂ K ₃ C ₂ K ₂ CKCK ₃) _S	31.0	14
C-3	(C ₅ K ₁₁) _S	21.0	B-4	(C ₃ K ₂ CKCK ₂ CKCK ₃) _S	31.0	18
C-2	(C ₃ K ₁₃) _S	11.9	B-6	[(CK) ₆ CK ₃] _S	31.0	26
C-1	(CK ₁₅) _S	3.8				
KFRP	(K ₁₆) _S	0				

* V_f = 58 - 63%

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The characteristics of impact load-deformation curves
Several kinds of Charpy impact load-deformation curves of HFRP are given in Fig.1. We can see:

a. The number of impact peaks of hybrid composites differs from each other because of containing different types of fibre: for C/G, there are three peaks, which implies a three-stage failure; while for C/K, there are only two peaks, which means a two-stage failure.

b. The shape of impact peaks varies with hybrid ratio. As V_{cf} increases, peaks become narrow.

c. Secondary peak vanishes as interface number increases.

d. Peak area is affected by the type of matrix.

2. Impact Ductility Index (DI)

The measured DI is shown in Fig.2. It is not difficult to find out the general tendency that the variation of DI for three kinds of HFRP with V_{cf} is similar. But DI for LER-C/K is higher than that for HER-C/K. Furthermore, it can be seen from Table.2 that DI for C-4 (interface number is 2) is larger than that for series B, and its fracture section is shown in Fig.3. This result accords with that obtained by Mallick et al. This is because KFRP in the core of sandwich structure can not only make full use of stiffness of CFRP, but also prevent the surface cracks from propagating towards the core.

Table.2 The relationship between DI and interface number of HER-C/K

No. of Sample	C-4	B-1	B-2	B-3	B-4	B-6
interface number	2	6	10	14	18	26
DI	3.4	2.7	1.8	1.6	2.5	4.2

3. Impact strength (α_k)

a. Effect of hybrid ratio

The values for α_k of C/G and C/K-HFRP lie between those of CFRP and GFRP, and CFRP and KFRP, respectively. And they decrease as V_{cf} increases (see Fig.4). It is because the content of tough fibres in hybrid composites is reduced.⁴ In addition, when using the same matrix of LER, α_k for C/G is higher than that for C/K. This indicates that as for improving impact ductility, GF is preferred to KF.

b. Effect of interface number and matrix

α_k for C/K varies hardly with interface number (see Fig.4), i.e. α_k is not affected by stacking form. In addition, for the same C/K hybridization, α_k differs from each other because of different matrices.

c. A model for estimating α_k

By processing a number of impact peaks obtained from the experiments, we suggest a triangular shape peak model as shown in Fig.5. The dotted line is the impact peak of CFRP and the solid line is that of HFRP. We suppose:

$$OA = L(c), \quad OC = l_i(c), \quad CA = l_p(c)$$

$$OB = L(H_y), \quad DB = l_p(H_y), \quad OD = l_i(H_y)$$

i.e.:

$$L(c) = l_i(c) + l_p(c), \quad L(H_y) = l_i(H_y) + l_p(H_y)$$

Moreover, considering hybrid effect coefficient, we can provide a formula for estimating impact strength:

$$\alpha_k = \frac{K}{2} \cdot \sigma_{\max}(c)(1+R\sigma)[l(c) + l_i(c)R_i + l_p(c)R_p] \quad (1)$$

where: K is modifying coefficient for peak shape and it is dependent on matrix, fibre, hybrid ratio and interface number. Here, when $V_{cf} < 30\%$, we take $K=1.2$; when $V_{cf} = 30\%$, we take $K=1.1$. The meaning of other symbols will be given in the latter part. The computed values for α_k from equation (1) are also given in Fig.4 (solid line). They are in good agreement with experimental ones.

4. Impact hybrid effect

Hybrid effect (abbreviated as HYE) is a special mechanical characteristic. In general, we can use a relative parameter -- hybrid effect coefficient R to describe the amount of HYE. R will have different values according to different definitions of HYE.

a. The Definition of the hybrid effect coefficient $R\alpha_k$ based on energy is as follows:

$$R\alpha_k = \frac{\alpha_k(H_y) - \alpha_k(c)}{\alpha_k(c)} \quad (2)$$

where: $\alpha_k(H_y)$ and $\alpha_k(c)$ are impact strength of HFRP and CFRP respectively. The computed values for $R\alpha_k$ are listed in Table 3. It can be seen that $R\alpha_k$ decreases as V_{cf} increases and is not affected by interface number. However, $R\alpha_k$ for LER-C/K is much higher than that for HER-C/K.

b. The hybrid effect coefficient R_L based on deformation is defined as:

$$R_L = \frac{L(H_y) - L(c)}{L(c)} \quad (3)$$

where: $L(H_y)$ and $L(c)$ are the total impact deformation of HFRP and CFRP respectively. The values are listed in Table 3.

c. The hybrid effect coefficient R_t based on partial deformation is defined as:

$$R_t = R_i + R_p \quad (4)$$

$$R_i = \frac{l_i(H_y) - l_i(c)}{l_i(c)} \quad (5)$$

$$R_p = \frac{l_p(H_y) - l_p(c)}{l_p(c)} \quad (6)$$

where: $l_i(H_y)$ and $l_i(c)$ are elastic deformation of HFRP and CFRP respectively; $l_p(H_y)$ and $l_p(c)$ are crack propagation deformation of HFRP and CFRP respectively. The values for R_t , R_i and R_p are also given in Table 3. We can see that R_i is much less than R_p , i.e. R_p/R_i is much larger. It indicates that the addition of GF or KF to CFRP mainly enhances the failure propagation deformation of CFRP. R_i and R_p vary with different matrices. The values for LER are higher than that for HER. Therefore,

R_i , R_p and R_t not only reflect the matching action between matrix and fibre, but also can be used to reveal the mechanism of toughening action of tough fibres.

d. The Definition of the hybrid effect coefficient $R\sigma$ based on maximum stress is as follows:

$$R\sigma = \frac{\sigma_{\max}(H_y) - \sigma_{\max}(c)}{\sigma_{\max}(c)} \quad (7)$$

where: $\sigma_{\max}(H_y)$ and $\sigma_{\max}(c)$ are the maximum impact stresses of HFRP and CFRP respectively. $R\sigma$ is also given in Table 3. It is easy to find out that almost all $R\sigma$ are negative. This indicates that the $\sigma_{\max}(c)$ of CFRP decreases with the addition of tough fibres. the decreasing degree with the addition of KF is much larger than that of GF.

Table 3 The hybrid effect coefficient

System	No.	R_i	R_p	R_t	R_p/R_i	R_L	$R\alpha K$	$R\sigma$
LER-C/G	C-1	1.50	14.7	16.2	9.6	6.7	3.9	-0.17
	C-2	1.42	15.1	16.5	10.6	7.0	4.2	-0.11
	C-3	1.54	14.9	16.4	9.7	6.9	3.9	0.05
	C-4	0.72	13.3	14.5	18.0	5.8	2.9	0.08
	C-5	0.31	18.9	19.2	61	7.8	3.2	0.075
	C-7	0.34	17.9	18.2	53	7.4	7.8	-0.02
LER-C/K	C-1	1.81	16.9	18.7	9.6	7.8	2.43	-0.27
	C-2	2.1	16.7	18.8	8.0	8.0	2.53	-0.24
	C-3	1.55	15.4	17.0	9.9	7.2	2.28	-0.21
	C-4	0.81	14.8	15.6	18.3	6.7	1.9	-0.34
	C-5	0.46	17.1	17.6	37.0	7.2	1.75	-0.10
	C-7	0.23	17.8	18.0	77.4	7.4	1.46	-0.25
HER-C/K	C-1	0.09	10.4	10.5	116	3.0	0.49	-0.43
	C-2	-0.09	12.5	12.4	-136	3.3	0.38	-0.33
	C-3	0.12	9.9	10.0	83	2.7	0.44	-0.39
	C-4	-0.18	12.4	12.2	-69	3.2	0.49	-0.37
	C-5	-0.18	9.3	9.1	-52	2.4	0.34	-0.35
	C-7	-0.50	11.0	10.5	-22	2.6	0.29	-0.27
HER-C/K	B-1	-0.03	11.0	11.0	-440	3.0	0.49	---
	B-2	-0.25	13.4	13.1	-54	3.5	0.59	---
	B-3	0.04	10.4	10.4	254	2.8	0.44	---
	B-4	-0.28	11.7	11.4	-42	3.0	0.47	---
	B-6	-0.42	11.0	10.6	-26	2.7	0.44	---

The above definitions of R help us to understand toughening mechanism of tough fibres from different aspects. This is very useful for further investigating impact properties of HFRP.

CONCLUSIONS

1. α_k and DI are both strongly dependent on hybrid ratio, matrix and fibre type. But α_k has no apparent relationship with interface number. Only when both of α_k and DI are relatively larger, can we say that the materials have good ductility.
2. As for improving impact ductility of CFRP, GF is preferred to KF.
3. The model established in this work can be used for well estimating the impact strength of hybrid composites. Furthermore, it relates all kinds of the definitions of R.
4. The various definitions of R reflect the amount of dynamic hybrid effect from different aspects. They all depend on hybrid ratio, interface number. Especially R_i and R_p can reflect the toughening mechanism of tough fibres.

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Fig.1 The load-deformation curves for Charpy impact

Fig. 2 The relation between DI and hybrid ratio

Fig.3 The SEM of impact fracture section of HER-C/K

Fig.4 The relation between α_k and hybrid ratio

Fig.5 The modelling diagram of impact peak